

Breeding and Genetics of Drought-Tolerant in Cowpea [*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp.]

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Abstract

The impact of drought on cowpea production in sub-Saharan Africa cannot be overemphasized. However, the use of drought-tolerant cowpea would help mitigate the effect of drought on cowpea production. Hence, the study aimed to breed drought-tolerant cowpea cultivars and determine the genetics of drought tolerance in cowpea. IT98K-205-8 and NG/SA/01/09/004 previously identified as drought tolerant and susceptible were reciprocally crossed in this study. Seeds of both F₁ and F₂ (selfed hybrids) progenies developed were screened for drought tolerance under simulated 35 days of water stress. Data was taken for drought stress and recovery response when water was re-introduced after drought simulation. A total of 49 hybrid progenies were gotten from the reciprocal crosses of the parents selected and screened in both F₁ and F₂ generations. Eleven droughts tolerant (85-100% recovery from drought) and nineteen moderate droughts tolerant (50-79% recovery from drought) were developed. A segregation ratio of 9:7 for drought tolerant to drought susceptible signifying duplicate recessive genes was observed in the F₂ population and inheritance of drought tolerant trait was independent on the mother plants. Hence, this information will be of vital use in the development of breeding strategies for drought-tolerant improvement in cowpea.

Keywords: Drought, recovery, tolerant, water stress, wilting

1.0 Introduction

The role of cowpea (*Vigna unguiculata* L. Walp) in food security in many developing countries in Africa and Asia cannot be over-emphasized. It is an important multipurpose crop plant mostly used for consumption and income generation at both local and international levels. Apart from being the cheapest source of protein available, it is also used as fodder for animal feed [8,1, 14]. However, its production has been reported marred by climatic factors, drought being the most prevalent among others.

Drought has been defined as the effects of a sustained lack of soil moisture required for the plant to properly grow and provide sufficient crop yield [17]. Although cowpea can do well with minimal

drought stress, estimated reductions of up to ~70% in cowpea yields have been reported across sub-Saharan Africa when drought stress is prolonged [11,18].

Several methods which include selection, breeding and introduction of drought-tolerant varieties, and regular irrigation during the planting season, to mention a few are developed by the breeders to ameliorate drought stress and improve crop production. However, breeding for drought-tolerant cultivars/varieties is one of the most cost-effective ways to cope with the effects of insufficient water supplies on crops. Research aiming at identifying drought-tolerant cultivars has recently become of interest because doing so is critical to delivering substantial information to plant breeders [17].

Fatokun[11]reported the challenges in screening for drought tolerance in cowpea due to uncontrolled factors, including temperature and water transmission within the soil apart from complex mechanisms entailed in identifying reliable traits for assessing drought tolerance in cowpea. However, the most sensitive stage in cowpea to drought stress is the seedling stage [2]. Hence, phenotyping drought tolerance at the seedling stage in a controlled condition could contribute toward advancing breeding programs for drought tolerance in cowpea. The development of cowpea cultivars/varieties with enhanced levels of drought tolerance is therefore a necessity if improved yield in cowpea is to be maintained. It is based on this premise that this study was set to develop drought-tolerant cultivars of cowpea.

2.0 Materials and Methods

2.1 Study area

This study was carried out at the Moore Plantation, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, screen house, IAR&T, Ibadan, Oyo State (Latitude: 7° 22' 35.2"N, Longitude: 3° 50' 34.4"E).

2.2 Sample collection, planting, and development of progeny

Seeds samples of IT98K-205-8 and NG/SA/01/09/004 previously identified as drought tolerant and drought susceptible respectively by [11], were collected from the International Institute of Tropical Agriculture (IITA), Ibadan, and Institute for Agricultural Research and Training (IAR&T), Ibadan, as parent breeding materials for the study. These parent seeds were planted three seeds/pot and were pruned down to one stand/pot (after two weeks of establishment) in 50 plastic buckets each of 2 kg pots equidistance from each other in the screen house, IAR&T, Ibadan, Oyo State (Latitude: 7° 22' 35.2"N, Longitude: 3° 50' 34.4"E). At maturity, reciprocal crosses were made between selected parent materials. Hybrid seeds, from F₁ pods, were harvested from mother plants and were thereafter planted single seed per pot to obtain the F₁ plant generation. Seeds derived from the F₁ plants (F₂ seeds) were also planted to obtain the F₂ plant generation. Backcrosses were also made between F₁ progenies and both parents, respectively.

2.3 Drought-tolerant screening of developed progenies

Drought-tolerant screening was carried out on both F₁ and F₂ plants in the screen house at IAR & T, Moore Plantation, Ibadan, Oyo State, Nigeria, using a modified protocol of [19] alongside both drought-tolerant and susceptible parents as checks. Three wooden boxes (each box representing a replicate) of 240 cm × 116 cm × 20 cm were made from a plank of 2.5 cm thickness. The boxes were lined with polyethene and filled up to a depth of 16 cm with air-dried and sieved topsoil collected from the southern farm of IAR & T, Ibadan. Equidistant holes were made in straight rows 10 cm apart with a hill-hill distance of 5 cm within the rows. Three cowpea seeds per individual plant were sown in a hole 2 cm deep and later thinned to one plant two weeks after germination. The boxes were watered daily for two weeks to establish the seedlings, and watering was stopped for the next thirty-five days (7 weeks). Wilted plants in each replicate for progeny plants were counted daily. Watering was then resumed for fourteen days (2 weeks) to ascertain the regeneration percentage for each variety.

2.4 Data collection and analysis

Data generated from the study were subjected to statistical analysis using SAS version 9.0.

The percentage of wilted plants/day (% *w_p*) was calculated using the formula in equation 1

$$\% WP = \frac{N_{pw}}{N_{ps}} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation I}$$

Where *N_{pw}* is the number of plants wilted and *N_{ps}* is the number of plant stands.

Percentage recovery was estimated after watering had resumed for fourteen days (two weeks) as shown in equation II.

$$\% \text{Rec} = \frac{N_{pr}}{N_{pw}} \times 100 \dots \dots \dots \text{Equation II}$$

Where *N_{pr}* is the number of plants that recovered after water stress, and *N_{pw}* is the total number of plants that wilted.

3.0 Results

3.1 Cross ability evaluation between parent materials

A total of 227 crosses were made between IT98K-205-8 (drought tolerant, DT) and NG/SA/01/09/004 (drought susceptible, DS) in the study, 132 crosses in the morning and 95 crosses in the evening (Table

1). Of the morning crosses, 15 successful crosses of the 105 crosses made on DS mother plants were observed. This was significant ($\chi^2=8.00$, $p < 0.01$) higher than the 3 successful crosses observed among

27 crosses made on DT mother plants in the study. In all the crosses, success was only achieved when the crossing was done in the morning compared to the evening as no success was observed on both mother plants during the evening crosses (Table 1).

Table 1: Cross-evaluation between IT98K-205-8 (DT) and NG/SA/01/09/004 (DS)

Crosses ($\text{♀} + \text{♂}$)	Morning (S)%	Evening (S)%	Total (S)%	χ^2
$P_1 \times P_2$	105 (15) ^{14.29%}	51 (0) ^{0%}	156 (15) ^{9.62%}	18.69**
$P_2 \times P_1$	27 (3) ^{11.11%}	44 (0) ^{0%}	71 (3) ^{4.23%}	4.07*
Total	132(18**) ^{13.64%}	95 (0) ^{0%}	227 (18) ^{7.93%}	6.03**
χ^2	46.09** (8.00**)	0.52	31.83** (8.00**)	

*, ** Significant at $p < 0.05$ and significant at $p < 0.01$ respectively; ♀ : mother (recipient) plant, ♂ : Father (Donor) plant, P_1 : drought tolerant parent (IT98K-205-8), P_2 : drought susceptible parent (NG/SA/01/09/004); (S): number of successful crosses that yielded pods; % percentage number of successful crosses that yielded pods

Cross evaluation between mother plants revealed that although there was a significant difference ($\chi^2=31.83$, $p < 0.01$) in the number of crosses made on both plant materials as mother plants, there was a significant difference in the number of successful pods set on mother plants, likewise, percentage abortion observed on mother plants (Table 2). The drought tolerance line (IT98K-205-8) had a significantly higher number of crosses, number of successful crosses, number of aborted crosses, total F_1 seeds from hybrid pods, average seed/pod and non-viable seeds ($p < 0.01$) than the drought-susceptible line (NG/SA/01/09/004) while

percentage aborted crosses (95.77%). The percentage of non-viability of seeds was higher in the drought susceptible than in the drought tolerance genotype. Average seeds per pod also significantly differ between mother plants ($\chi^2=5.50$, $p < 0.05$). A total number of 104 hybrid seeds collected from 15 pods from DT mother plants was also significantly ($\chi^2=95.34$, $p < 0.01$) higher than the 3 hybrid seeds derived from the three pods obtained from DS mother plants. The study showed that all sampled seeds from DS mother plants were not viable while 49 (47.12%) hybrid seeds from DT mother plants were viable (Table 2).

Table 2: Breeding evaluation on recipient plants IT98K-205-8 (DT) and NG/SA/01/09/004 (DS)

Evaluation	IT98K-205-8	NG/SA/01/09/004	Total	χ^2
Number of crosses	156	71	227	31.83**
Number of successful crosses	15	3	18	8.00**
Percentage successful crosses	9.62%	4.23%	7.93%	
Number of aborted crosses	141	68	209	25.50**
Percentage aborted crosses	90.38%	95.77%	92.07%	
Total F_1 seeds from hybrid pods	104	3	107	95.34**
Average seed/pod	7	1	8	4.50*
Total viable seeds	49	0	49	**
Percentage viability	47.12%	0.00%		
Non-viable seeds	55	3	58	46.62**
Percentage non-viability	52.88%	100.00%		

*, **Significant at $p < 0.05$ and $p < 0.01$ respectively; IT98K-205-8: Drought tolerant parent; NG/SA/01/09/004: Drought Susceptible parent

3.2 Drought tolerance performance and segregation pattern among hybrids

The ability to withstand drought was evaluated in the 49 developed progenies using the rate of percentage wilting during the water stress period and percentage recovery after water stress at both F₁ and F₂ generations. All sampled F₁ hybrid plants showed a tolerance response similar to the susceptible parent material. However, the study

revealed three clustered groups with eleven (11) hybrids clustering with the DT parent, nineteen (19) clustering with the DS parent and 19 hybrid plants moderately drought tolerant within the F₂ generation plants. The distribution of sampled F₂ hybrids showed a 9:7 segregation ratio pattern ($\chi^2 = 0.49$, $p = 0.48$). An indicative of duplicate recessive gene action (Figure 1, Table 3).

Figure 1: Dendrogram from Euclidean paired group cluster of 49 F₃ population with the two parent lines

Table 3: Drought tolerance response among developed F₁ and F₂ hybrid plants

Drought Rating	Drought Susceptible	Drought Moderate	Drought Tolerant
IT98K-205-8	-	-	50
NG/SA/01/09/004	50	-	-
F ₁	49	-	-
F ₂	19	19	11
Percentage wilting (%)			
Day 12	0 – 50	0 – 50	0 – 16.67
Day 24	25 – 100	33.33 – 66.67	0. – 66.67
Day 35	100	66.67 – 100	50 – 100
Percentage Recovery (%)	0 – 45	50 – 85	85 – 100

IT98K-205-8: drought tolerant parent; NG/SA/01/09/004: drought susceptible parent; F₁: hybrids from DT x DS; F₂: hybrids selfed F₁ plants

The study showed that there was a gradual rise in the percentage of wilting among the F₂ hybrid plants with the highest wilting observed in both the drought-susceptible and moderately drought-tolerant genotypes. By day 24, most of the DS hybrids showed ~100% wilting while 66.67% wilting was observed in some of the MDT and DT hybrids evaluated. All DS hybrids showed 100% wilting by day 35, MDT hybrids showed 66.67-100% wilting while DT hybrids showed 50-100% wilting. On watering the hybrid plants after drought tolerant assay, percentage recovery (%Rec) response among hybrids varied. DS hybrids showed the least recovery (%Rec = 0-45%), MDT showed moderate recovery (%Rec = 50-79) while most of the DT hybrids showed PR ranging between 85-100% in the study (Table 3).

4.0 Discussion

Hybridization during cowpea breeding programs recorded varied degrees of success. The success of hybridization between plants is dependent on varied factors which include pollen pistil compatibility, recipient genotype, and favourable climatic factors to mention a few [4]. However, from this present study, successful crosses obtained during the morning hybridization might be indicative of favourable environmental factors surrounding the cross as compared to the hybridization outcome for the evening crosses, similar to reports of [4]. Ogunsola and Igun, [16] have reported successful crosses in the early hours of the day during hybridization experiments in cowpea. Although crosses made on respective parents significantly differ, the success rate on the mother plants, regardless of genotype, is in proximity. This indicates no genotype effect on the success of hybridisation in cowpea of the close relationship as compared to similar studies on distant relatives, which reported a genotype effect [6,7]. This is contrary to the

report of Amusa et al. [3], who observed a maternal inclination of the offspring from the hybridization process during their study.

Low successful crosses of an average of 13% were obtained in this study. This low success rate agrees with crosses involving cowpea genotypes obtained in previous studies [14]. Various reasons have been attributed to the failures of successful crosses in cowpea which include cross combinations, genetic divergence and environmental factors [10, 14]. The low success rate in the intraspecific crosses in this study may also be attributed to pre- and post-fertilization barriers such as pollen-pistil incompatibility, embryo abortion, environmental factors and the close pollination nature of cowpea being a cleistogamous crop plant [4].

A high number of unviable hybrid seeds have been reported to accompany interspecific crosses [4, 12, 14]. Although, some authors have reported that hybrids from crosses with some wild and weedy relatives of cowpea gave good reproductive potentials [13]. This might probably be due to the relative genetic distance between the germplasms crossed. However, a high percentage of viable hybrids was observed in this study, which may be a result of the genetic closeness of the parental genotypes used. This corroborates the postulate made by Singh [20] that the closer the species involved in the cross are genetically, the easier the development of the hybrids from the parents and the more fertile the progenies. The works of Amusa et al. [4] also revealed that the timing of a cross also plays a significant role in the successful or unsuccessful outcome of the cross.

Success in breeding for drought tolerance in cowpea has been reportedly marred due to the lack of simple, cheap, and reliable screening methods to select

drought-tolerant plants and progenies from the segregating populations [19]. Also, attempts to improve the drought tolerance of cowpea through conventional breeding programs have met with limited success because drought tolerance is physiologically and genetically a complex trait [2, 9]. Hence, breeders are interested in developing drought-tolerant lines and uncovering the genetics or pattern of inheritance. Such information could be incorporated into drought-tolerant programmes in crop improvement. The study successfully developed eleven hybrid genotypes with approximately 85-100% recovery rate using both percentage wilting and recovery after 35 days of water stress simulation at the seedling stage. These genotypes could provide the needed genes to improve the cowpea gene pool for drought tolerance.

Understanding the mechanism of inheritance of an important trait like drought tolerance cannot be over-emphasized. Such information would be of immense benefit in the design of a drought-tolerant breeding programme for cowpea. Segregation pattern among hybrids and the F₂ generation evaluated in this study revealed duplicate recessive genes controlling drought tolerance in cowpea while the absence of drought tolerance in F₁ plants from the drought tolerant parent implies that the inheritance of drought tolerance is independent of the mother plants [5]. This does not corroborate the hypothesized quantitative traits loci and candidate gene association with drought tolerance proposed by Agbicodo et al. [2]. This difference could be dependent on the nature of drought tolerance measuring traits used which include, water use efficiency, water potential, turgidity, relative water content, chlorophyll stability index, and diffusion pressure deficit to mention a few.

Conclusion

This study developed eleven drought tolerance cowpea genotypes with 85-100% recovery which could go a long way in the mitigation of the water stress effect on Nigeria's cowpea yield. However, it is very important to understand the nature and inheritance of this trait if a successful breeding program is developed. The study revealed that genes controlling drought ability in cowpea segregated in a ratio 9:7 for drought tolerant to drought susceptible in the F₂ generation plants implying a duplicate recessive genes action. This information will be handy in the development of marker-assisted breeding strategies for cowpea improvement in this regard.

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